

Blue-green algae multiplication in freshwater ponds and ditches

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

An easy method of multiplying blue-green algae (BGA) was standardized in 1977 — the algae are simply incubated in the rice field with water. Further study showed that abundantly available small, shallow, stagnant ponds and ditches in almost all the villages of Tanjore district in Tamil Nadu can be used as multiplication sites of BGA during summer (Mar-Jun). A survey showed species of *Gloeotrichia*, *Nostoc*, *Aphanothece*, *Cylindrospermum*, *Anabaena*, *Aulosira*, *Plectonema*, and *Scytonema* growing in freshwater tanks and ditches. The details

for multiplication follow:

1. If the channel water is stopped, multiplication can be carried out; otherwise, the water inlet and outlet have to be closed.
2. The composite BGA inoculum is applied at 3 kg/40 m².
3. No fertilizer application is necessary.
4. No daphnid problem was observed under this system of multiplication. Only very small conical types of snails and water beetles were observed. Because the damage caused was negligible, no pesticidal application was warranted.
5. Within a month, depending on the suitability of inoculum, the BGA growth over the water surface was dense or sparse.
6. The BGA floating on the water

surface was collected and dried in the sun by spreading over a thin layer of powdered soil on a threshing floor.

7. Subsequent harvests were once in 3–5 weeks. Fresh application of inoculum was not necessary.

8. The yield ranged from 10 to 40 kg/40 m². A higher yield of BGA was obtained with *Gloeotrichia*, *Nostoc*, and *Aphanothece*.

9. If subsequent BGA multiplication is done in the same place, fresh application of BGA inoculum is not necessary.

If the Government undertakes the inoculation of shallow ponds and ditches with useful composite BGA for one season, the farmers can simply collect the algal seed material in the following years. ■

Announcements

Philippine Inventors Contest prize for transplanter

John A. Mc Mennamy, formerly head, Design Engineering Section, and Ignacio Manalili, assistant design engineer, International Rice Research Institute, were recently awarded a silver medal and ₱10,000 in cash in the Philippine Inventors Contest for their work on the design and development of a five-row manually operated transplanting machine for rice paddy (photos 1, 2).

This year's theme for the annual Philippine Inventors Contest was "Inventions for Food and Energy for Basic Human Needs." Designs of inventions covering applications in agriculture and industry were judged on degree of originality and creativity, extent of usefulness, and potential for commercial viability. The design for the IRRI transplanting machine was recently released for commercial production. One man can transplant from 1/4 to 1/3 ha/day with the machine. Total labor requirements are reduced from about 120 labor days/ha with conventional hand transplanting methods, to less than 60 labor days/ha with the manually operated machine. For more information, contact the IRRI Agricultural Engineering Department. ■

1. Rice transplanting machines being tested at IRRI.

2. The manually operated five-row machine is composed of a sled, seedling tray, and simple three-position picking mechanism activated by depressing the handle.